

Toxicological Evaluation of *Cassia occidentalis* Leaf Extracts: Unveiling the Safety Profile of a Traditional Remedy

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Abstract:

People assume that ayurvedic medications have fewer adverse effects than allopathic medications. Our study must determine the toxicity of the medicinal plants to ensure the safety of using these plants and their preparations (in gel and powder form). The aim of this study was to evaluate the acute toxicity of *Cassia occidentalis* leaves for medicinal purposes. Swiss mice received an oral dose of 2000 mg/kg body weight in the acute toxicity investigation. The different *Cassia occidentalis* extracts were administered orally to Swiss mice in a single dose then recorded the changes in body weight, food and water intake, and observations from the cage side. Our study revealed that the plant material was non-toxic.

Key words: *Cassia occidentalis*; Sub-acute toxicity, Lipid Profile, LD₅₀

Introduction

The use of herbal drugs for the management of certain ailments continues unabated in the most developing communities due to easy access and for economic reasons. Plants, therefore, remain the main source of the active drugs from a natural source and are still indispensable in the traditional medicine for treating a number of diseases (Ogbonnia, *et al.*, 2008). The traditional indigenous systems of medicine contain active organic compounds, and are employed in the treatment of diseases of diverse origins. Traditional medicines are used by about 60% of the world population both in the developing countries and developed countries where modern medicines are predominantly used (Mythilypriya, *et al.*, 2007). The World Health Organisation (WHO) survey indicates that about 70 – 80 % of the world's population relies on non-

conventional medicine, mainly of herbal source in the primary health care (Pieme, *et al.*, 2006). Experimental screening method is, therefore, important to ascertain the safety and efficacy of herbal products as well as to establish the active components of these herbal remedies (Tedong, *et al.*, 2007). To determine the safety of the plant products for human use, toxicological evaluation such as hepatotoxicity, CNS toxicity and renal toxicity should be carried out in various experimental animals to predict the toxicity and to provide guidelines for selecting a 'safe' dose in humans (Mukinda, 2007). But it is quite difficult to ascertain certain adverse effects in animals such as headache, abdominal pain, dizziness and visual disturbances. In addition, interspecies differences in the pharmacokinetic parameters make it difficult to translate some adverse effects from animals and humans. Nevertheless, the evaluation of adverse effects of sub-acute and acute dosing in experimental animals may be more relevant in determining the overall toxicity of the plant preparation. Acute studies with a range of doses have to be conducted first to select proper dose(s) for acute and sub-acute studies; the doses selected for acute and sub-acute toxicity studies should be at and above the suggested human dose (Rhiouani, *et al.*, 2008). The present study was carried out to assess the toxicity of Petroleum ether extract of *Cassia occidentalis* (PECO), Ethyl acetate extract of *Cassia occidentalis* (EACO) and Ethanolic extract of *Cassia occidentalis* (ETCO). In addition to compare with all the extracts, ETCO showed a promising *in vitro* antioxidant activity and Preliminary phytochemical studies showed that ethanolic extract of *Cassia occidentalis* contain various pharmacological responsible compounds (Olson, *et al.*, 2000).. So PECO, EACO and ETCO extracts were subjected to acute toxicity studies and ETCO was subjected to sub-acute toxicity studies to further confirm these activities using animals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of Different Plant Extracts:

Cassia occidentalis leaves were collected from the forest of Kalakatu, Tirunelveli District, India. Taxonomic identification was made from botanical survey of medicinal plants, Siddha Unit, Government of India, Palayamkottai. Fresh plant leaves were shade dried at room temperature, ground into fine powder, and then extracted (amount 500 g) with solvents such as petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, and ethanol by increasing polarity of each solvents at a particular time interval for 24 hours by continuous hot extraction using the soxhlet apparatus at a temperature of 60°C. The extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary

evaporator to constant weight. The extracts were collected and preserved in a desiccator until used for further studies.

Acute Toxicity Study with Petroleum Ether, Ethyl Acetate and Ethanolic Extracts of *Cassia occidentalis*

Determination of acute oral toxicity is usually the initial screening step in the assessment and evaluation of the toxic characteristics of all compounds. The types of toxicity tests which are routinely performed by pharmaceutical manufacturers in the investigation of a new drug involve acute, sub-acute and chronic toxicity assays. Acute toxicity assay involved the estimation of LD₅₀ (the dose which has proved to be lethal (causing death) to 50% of the tested group of animals). Acute oral toxicity of petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and ethanolic extract of *Cassia occidentalis* was carried out as per the guidelines Organization of Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD – 423) guidelines. The albino mice of 20-25 g were fasted over night and provided only water, after which the extracts were administered by gastric intubations to relevant group of animals orally at the dose of 5 mg/kg body weight in Tween-80. The animals were observed for 14 days and maintained with normal food. Mortality rate of 2 or 3 animals in 14 days were recorded and the dose is said to be toxic. But when mortality of one animal was observed, then the same dose is repeated again for confirmation. However, when mortality was not observed, the procedure was repeated for further higher doses such as 50, 300 and 2,000 mg/kg body weight. Toxic symptoms were observed for 72 hours including behavioural changes, locomotion, convulsions and mortality. The same method was followed for the acute toxicity study of other extracts.

Cage side Observations

Observations include changes in skin and fur, eyes and mucous membranes, and also respiratory, circulatory, autonomic and central nervous systems, and somato motor activity and behaviour pattern, special attention is directed for the observation of tremors, convulsions, salivation, diarrhoea, lethargy, sleep and coma.

Body Weight, Food and Water Intake

Body weight, food and water intake were recorded at two-days intervals.

Pathology

Surviving animals were fasted overnight, weighed and humanely killed on the 15th day using anesthetic ether. All test animals were subjected to gross necroscopy.

Sub-acute toxicity study for Ethanolic Extracts of *Cassia occidentalis*

This experiment evaluates the toxicity potential of *Cassia occidentalis* i.e. this study evaluates the protection of the extracts of *Cassia occidentalis*. Wistar rats (160 ± 10 g) were used for the present study. The animals are divided into seven groups of six animals in each group. The dose of the extract was calculated based on the body weight of the animal. The animals in group I are administered with a single daily dose of 0.5 ml of Tween 80 orally for 20 days. The animals in Group II and III were administered with 100 mg/kg body weight of ethanolic extracts of *Cassia occidentalis*. The animals in Group IV and V were administered with 250 mg/kg body weight of ethanolic extracts of *Cassia occidentalis*. The animals in Group VI and VII were administered with 500 mg/kg body weight of ethanolic extracts of *Cassia occidentalis* respectively for 20 days orally. The animals are then weighed every five days, from the start of the treatment, to record the weight variation. At the end of the treatment, blood samples were collected by puncturing retro orbital plexus after mild anaesthesia for biochemical analysis and the liver tissues were collected for histopathological studies. The collected blood sample was centrifuged within 5 minute of collection at 4000 mg for 10 minute to obtain plasma, which was analysed for total cholesterol, total glyceride, HDL, LDL, plasma glucose, alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST).

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM. The statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison tests using Instat-3 software package (Graph pad), Prism Ltd, USA.

Results

Acute Toxicity Study of PECO, EACO and ETCO

The acute toxicity of PECO, EACO and ETCO were carried out as per OECD-423 guidelines for safe dose administration to animals. The results of acute toxicity study revealed that LD₅₀ values of PECO, EACO and ETCO extract of both the plants were high and apparently showed the safety of those extracts. The zero percent mortality for various extracts of CO was

found at the doses of 5, 50, 300 and 2000 mg.kg⁻¹. In addition these animals were observed continuously for four hours at first instance, and then at an intervals of two hours up to 24 hours to examine any change in the mice behavior such as respiration, writhing, CNS excitation and depression, reflexes, muscular weakness, salivation, diarrhoea, food intake and mortality. The observation of gross behavioral studies revealed that after administration of PECO, EACO and ETCO showed normal respiratory parameters, salivary secretions, sense of touch and sound. The writhing reflex, tremor, convulsions and hind limb paralysis were absent. No alteration is found in GIT motility and induction of diarrhoea with these extracts.

Table 1: Effect of various extracts on behavioral activities on mice

Behaviour	Intervals of observation in (hrs)										
	Up to 4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20	22	24
Respiration	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Writhing	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tremor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Convulsions	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Hind limb paralysis	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sense of touch and sound	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Salivation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Diarrhoea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mortality	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Each behaviour was studied with three animals. Where “+” ve means “presence” and “-” ve means “absence” of specific behaviour.

Effect of ETCO in Sub-acute Toxicity

Effect of ETCO on Body Weight Changes in Mice

From the study it was observed that, there was significant change ($P < 0.05$) in body weight in all the animals observed when compared to control. where group I animals were treated with normal saline (5 ml/kg), group II and III animals with 50 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg of ETCO, group IV and V animals with 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg of ETCO.

Table 2: Effect of ETCO on Body Weight Changes in Mice

Treatment	Day 1	Day 5	Day 10	Day 20
Control	165.1 ± 1.1	167.4 ± 2.7	170.1 ± 2.1	171.3 ± 1.5
ETCO 50 mg/kg	151.2 ± 1.2	155.6 ± 2.1	169.3 ± 1.8	170.8 ± 1.5
ETCO 100 mg/kg	154.4 ± 2.2	169.4 ± 1.1	173.5 ± 1.3	178.2 ± 1.4
ETCO 250 mg/kg	167.1 ± 2.2	170.4 ± 1.1	172.4 ± 1.8	174.6 ± 1.3
ETCO 500 mg/kg	168.8 ± 1.4	170.6 ± 1.5	171.2 ± 1.1*	172.6 ± 1.1*

n=6. The statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test. * $P < 0.05$, compared to normal control group.

Figure 1: Effect of ETCO on Body Weight Changes in Mice

Effect of ETCO on Kidney, Heart, Liver and Brain in Mice

From the study it was clear that significant ($P < 0.01$) changes in the weights of various organs of the animals occurred with higher doses of the extract (500 mg/kg body weight), but macroscopic examinations did not show any changes in colour of the organs of the treated animals compared with the control. Group I animals were treated with normal saline (5 ml/kg), group II and III animals with 50 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg of ETCO, group IV and V animals with 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg of ETCO.

Table 3: Effect of ETCO on kidney, heart, liver and brain of the mice

Treatment	Heart (g)	Kidney (g)	Liver (g)	Brain (g)
Control	0.23 ± 0.04	0.53 ± 0.04	3.15 ± 0.03	0.57 ± 0.06
ETCO 50 mg/kg	0.24 ± 0.01	0.59 ± 0.06	3.32 ± 0.09	0.62 ± 0.09
ETCO 100 mg/kg	0.28 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.02	3.49 ± 0.05	0.68 ± 0.02
ETCO 250 mg/kg	0.32 ± 0.05	0.88 ± 0.04	3.53 ± 0.06	0.78 ± 0.05
ETCO 500 mg/kg	0.38 ± 0.03*	0.89 ± 0.05*	3.92 ± 0.04*	0.79 ± 0.08*

n=6. The statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test. * $P < 0.05$, compared to normal control group.

Figure 2: Effect of ETCO on kidney, heart, liver and brain of the Mice

Effect of ETCO on Biochemical Profiles of Mice

From the study it was evident that there was significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) in the plasma glucose level in treated Mice at dose of 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg compared with control Mice. Significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) in the plasma total cholesterol (TC), triglyceride (TG) and LDL – cholesterol levels were also observed. But a significant increase ($P < 0.05$) in HDL – cholesterol levels were observed in 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg animals compared with the control animals. Aspartate Transaminase (AST), Alanine Transaminase (ALT) and Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP) levels were also normal in the ETCO treated animals. From the results of biochemical study there were no evidence of severe toxicity associated with the administration of higher concentration of ETCO, where group I animals were treated with normal saline (5 ml/kg), group

II and III animals with 50 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg of ETCO, group IV and V animals with 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg of ETCO..

Table 4: Effects of ETCO on Biochemical Parameters Such as Glucose, Cholesterol, Triglyceride, HDL and LDL

Treatment	Glucose (mg/dl)	Cholesterol (mg/dl)	Triglyceride (mg/dl)	HDL (mg/dl)	LDL (mg/dl)
Control	98.45 ± 1.14	68.78 ± 0.40	36.20 ± 1.15	38.2 ± 0.30	82.02 ± 1.70
ETCO 50 mg/kg	93.13 ± 0.54	67.19 ± 1.02	35.13 ± 2.14	40.3 ± 1.43	80.18 ± 1.28
ETCO 100 mg/kg	85.69 ± 1.62	63.74 ± 0.06	33.33 ± 0.57	54.2 ± 0.17	77.15 ± 0.32
ETCO 250 mg/kg	82.96 ± 1.73*	58.18 ± 0.73*	25.33 ± 0.30*	71.4 ± 0.77*	62.50 ± 0.43*
ETCO 500 mg/kg	79.60 ± 1.32*	45.43 ± 1.50*	23.43 ± 1.08*	74.6 ± 0.25*	58.55 ± 0.76*

n=6. The statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test. * $P < 0.05$, compared to normal control group.

Figure 3: Effects of ETCO on Biochemical Parameters Such as Glucose, Cholesterol, Triglyceride, HDL and LDL

Effect of ETCO on Biochemical Parameters Such as AST, ALT and ALP

From the study it was evident that, there was a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) in AST, ALT and ALP level in the treated Mice at higher dose of 500 mg/kg as compared with the control.

Table 5: Effects of ETCO on Biochemical Parameters Such as AST, ALT and ALP

Treatment	AST (IU/L)	ALT (IU/L)	ALP (IU/L)
Control	234.4 ± 2.47	68.4 ± 1.78	245.60 ± 1.89
ETCO 50 mg/kg	231.9 ± 1.93	67.3 ± 1.09	241.58 ± 2.91
ETCO 100 mg/kg	228.2 ± 2.47	64.4 ± 1.02	237.60 ± 2.10
ETCO 250 mg/kg	211.2 ± 1.12	57.9 ± 1.54	229.91 ± 2.07
ETCO 500 mg/kg	201.6 ± 2.06*	49.8 ± 1.97*	215.61 ± 1.33*

n=6. The

statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test. * $P < 0.05$, compared to normal control group.

Figure 4: Effects of ETCO on Biochemical Parameters Such as AST, ALT and ALP

Effect of ETCO on Haematological Parameters in Mice

From the study it was evident that there was a significant increase ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the haemoglobin contents, RBC and WBC count in the group treated Mice especially at higher dose (500 mg/kg) compared with control Mice. Group I animals were treated with normal saline (5 ml/kg), group II and III animals with 50 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg of ETCO, group IV and V animals with 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg of ETCO.

Table 6: Effects of ETCO on Haematological Parameters Such as Haemoglobin, RBC and WBC

Treatment	Haemoglobin (mg/dl)	RBC (10^6 / mm^3)	WBC (10^6 / mm^3)
Control	10.2 ± 2.30	11.6 ± 1.03	11.3 ± 1.04
ETCO 50 mg/kg	10.5 ± 1.97	11.8 ± 2.18	11.9 ± 2.01
ETCO 100 mg/kg	12.4 ± 1.12	12.32 ± 0.04	12.2 ± 1.05
ETCO 250 mg/kg	13.1 ± 0.30	13.55 ± 0.45	13.6 ± 1.02
ETCO 500 mg/kg	13.3 ± 1.25*	13.80 ± 1.33*	13.9 ± 2.09*

n=6. The statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test. * $P < 0.05$, compared to normal control group.

Figure 5: Effect of ETCO on Heamatological Parameter in Haemoglobin

Figure 6: Effect of ETCO on Haematological Parameters in RBC

Figure 7: Effect of ETCO on Haematological Parameters in WBC

Effects of ETCO on Biochemical Parameters Such as Urea, Uric acid, Creatinine and Protein

From the study it was evident that there was a decrease ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the Urea, Uric acid, Creatinine and Protein in the group treated Mice especially at higher dose (500 mg/kg) compared with control Mice, where group I animals were treated with normal saline (5

ml/kg), group II and III animals with 50 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg of ETCO, group IV and V animals with 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg of ETCO.

Table 7: Effects of ETCO on Biochemical Parameters Such as Urea, Uric acid, Creatinine and Protein

Treatment	Urea (mg/dl)	Uric acid (mg/dl)	Creatinine (mg/dl)	Protein (mg/dl)
Control	3.23± 0.57	0.56 ± 0.05	0.74 ± 0.05	4.3 ± 0.2
ETCO 50 mg/kg	3.39 ±1.21	0.61 ± 0.02	0.80 ± 0.09	4.2 ± 0.6
ETCO 100 mg/kg	3.58± 0.53	0.76 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.03	4.6 ± 0.4
ETCO 250 mg/kg	2.87± 0.45	0.72 ± 0.01	0.87 ± 0.04	4.1 ± 0.8
ETCO 500 mg/kg	2.16 ±0.76	0.54 ± 0.09	0.64 ± 0.08	3.8 ± 0.3

n=6. The statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test. * $P < 0.05$, compared to normal control group.

Figure 6.7: Effects of ETCO on Biochemical Parameters Such as Urea, Uric acid, Creatinine and Protein

Discussion

The evaluation of sub-acute and acute dosing in experimental animals may be more relevant in determining the overall toxicity of the plant preparation. The highest overall concordance of toxicity in animals in comparison with humans is with haematological,

gastrointestinal, and cardiovascular adverse effects, while certain adverse effects in humans, especially hypersensitivity and idiosyncratic reactions, are poorly correlated with toxicity observed in animals (Olson, *et al.*, 2000). In the present study, where the acute toxicity study of ETCO was carried out as per OECD-423 guidelines, no mortality was observed in both the animals of the control group as well as animals treated with a maximum dose of 2000 mg/kg. Hence 1/10th of 2000 mg/kg i.e. 200 mg/kg of dose was selected as a maximum dose for sub-acute toxicity study (Abutaha, *et al.*, 2008). The results of sub-acute toxicity study showed that there was no significant change in animal behaviour due to the absence of toxicity. The animals treated with ETCO showed normal growth pattern and body weight compared with control Mice and treated with normal saline. So the changes in body weight can be used as an indicator of adverse effects of drugs and chemicals (Tofovic, 1999; Raza, *et al.*, 2002; Teo, 2002). The ethanol extract of CO at a dose of 500 mg.kg⁻¹ showed no significant changes in individual body weight, organ weight, biochemical parameters, free fatty acid, hematological and urinary parameters. The results are in agreement with previous studies using different plants. Animal behavior, food and water intake were normal during subacute toxicity study. Changes in body weight have been used to assess the course of the disease response to therapy of drugs (Varley, 1984). No significant changes were observed in hematological screening indicating the non toxic nature of the ethanol extract of CO. Plasma urea, uric acid and creatinine levels were increased in group V animals when compared with group I animals and it may be due to renal dysfunction. Since, the raised urea and non-protein nitrogen level in blood have been observed with impaired renal function or in acute renal failure (Varley, 1984). In the present study, the alteration is not considerable, the observed small decrease in the urinary contents is not sufficient to regard this change as due to acute renal failure (Watson and Malone, 1977). Hence, the CO did not induce any toxic effect in animal. From these it was observed that the ethanol extract of CO are non-toxic to carry out further studies such as analgesic, anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic activity in animal models.

Conflict of Interest

Nil

REFERENCES

- Abu Taha Nael, A., Alkawajah, M., Aziz Raveesha, K.K.** (2008). Acute and subacute toxicity studies of *Persea Americana* Mill (Avocado) seed in Mice. *International Journal of Medical Toxicology and Legal medicine* 11 (2), 10 – 16.
- Adeneye, A.A., Ajagbonna, O.P., Adeleke, T.I., Bello, S.O.** (2006). Preliminary toxicity and phytochemical studies of the stem bark aqueous extract of *Musanga cecropioides* in Mice. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 105, 374 – 379.
- Hayes, A.W.** (1989). Guidelines for acute oral toxicity testing. In: *Principles and Methods of Toxicity*. New York: Raven Press Ltd, 184.
- Mukinda, J.T., Syce, J.A.** (2007). Acute and acute toxicity of the aqueous extract of *Artemisia afra* in rodents. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 112, 138 – 144.
- Mythilipriya, R., Shanthi, P., Sachidanandam, P.** (2007). Oral acute and subacute toxicity studies with kalpamuthaa, a modified indigenous preparation on Mice. *Journal of health science* 53(4), 351 – 358.
- Ogbonnia, S., Adekunle, A.A., Bosa, M.K., Enwuru, V.N.** (2008). Evaluation of acute and subacute toxicity of *Alstonia congensis* Engler (Apocyanaceae) bark and *Xylopiia aethiopica* (Dunal) A. Rich (Annonaceae) fruits mixtures used in the treatment of diabetes. *African journal of Biotechnology* 7(6), 701 – 705.
- Olson, H., Betton, G., Robinson, D.** (2000). Concordance of toxicity of pharmaceuticals in humans and in animals, *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology* 32, 56 – 57.
- Pieme, C.A., Penlap, V.N., Nkegoum, B., Taziebou, C.L., Tekwu, E.M., Ngongang, J.** (2006). Evaluation of acute and subacute toxicities of aqueous ethanolic extract of leaves of (*L. Roxb*) (Cesalpiniaceae). *African journal of Biotechnology* 5(3), 283 – 289.
- Raza, M., Al-Shabanah, O.A., El-Hadiyah, T.M., Al-Majed, A.A.** (2002). Effect of prolonged vigabatrin treatment on haematological and biochemical parameters in plasma, liver and kidney of swiss albino mice. *Scientia Pharamceutica* 70, 135 – 145.
- Rhiouani, H., El-Hilaly, J., Zafar, H., Israeli., Badiaa Lyoussi.** (2008). Acute and sub-acute toxicity of an aqueous extract of the leaves of *Herniaria glabra* in rodents. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 118, 378 – 386.

Tedong, L., Paul desire Djomeni Dzeufiet., Theophile Dimo. (2007). Acute and subacute toxicity of *Anacardium occidentale* (Anacardiaceae) leaves hexane extract in mice. African journal of Traditional complementary and Alternative medicine 4(2), 140 – 147.

Teo, S., Stirling, D., Thomas, S., Hobermann, A., Kiorpes, A., Khetani, V. (2002). A 90 days oral gavage toxicity study of D- methyl penidate and DL methyl penidate in Sprague – Dawley Mice. Toxicology 179, 183.

Tofovic, S.P., Jackson, E.K. (1999). Effect of long term caffeine consumption on renal function in spontaneously hypertensive heart failure prone Mice. Journal of Cardiovascular Pharmacology 33, 360 – 366.

Varley. H., Gowenlock. AH and Bell. M. (1984). Vitamins. In: Practical clinical biochemistry, Eds. Varley, H. and Gowenlock, A.H. William Heinemann medical books Ltd., London Vol II, 215-217.

Watson. WC and Malone. MH. (1977). Evaluation of immunosuppressive potential of cryogenine using developing and established adjuvant arthritis in rats. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 66(9): 1304-1308.